

IMPACT OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING POLICY REFORM ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN SOUTH-SOUTH, NIGERIA

BY

AGWI Vincent I. A¹. Ph.D, OCHU Hart O. Ph.D²

¹Department of Industrial and Technology Education
Alvan Ikoku Federal University of Education, Owerri, Imo State

²Department of Industrial Technology Education
Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State.

Email: agwivincent2019@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20973275>

Abstract

The study assessed the impact of Technical and Vocational Education and Training Policy reform on sustainable development in South-South, Nigeria. Three research questions were posed and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population for the study consisted of 217 respondents made up of 172 male TVET educators and 45 female TVET educators in all the Universities in South-South, Nigeria that offer programmes in Industrial and Technology Education. Simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 male TVET educators while all the 45 female TVET educators were used in the study without sampling because their population size is considered manageable. The instrument used for data collection was a structured four-point rating scale questionnaire. The instrument was face and content validated by three (3) experts in Technology Education Department. Cronbach's alpha reliability method was employed to determine the internal consistency of the instrument which yielded a co-efficient of 0.80. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed among others, that Technical and Vocational Education and Training policy reform have not helped to achieve adequate sustainable development goals in South-South, Nigeria due to non-implementation of policy reform programmes in Technical and Vocational education and Training in South-South, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that government should ensure that stakeholders engagement in policy reform in Technical and Vocational Education and Training are strengthened, there is an urgent need for increase in funding for effective implementation of Technical and Vocational Education and Training programmes in South-South, Nigeria.

Keywords: Technical education, policy reform, sustainable development

Introduction

In Nigeria, Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is crucial for Nigerian's economic growth, poverty reduction and sustainable development (Akpan, 2024). Similarly, Ikpeazu and Ugwu (2025), Technical and Vocational Education and Training plays a vital role in equipping youths with practical skills required for employment and entrepreneurship for self-reliant upon graduation. Ejimaji and Nwankwo

(2023) posited that in Nigeria recent policy reforms aimed at enhancing TVET's relevance, quality and accessibility have been carried out at the past. However, the impact of these reforms according to Ibekwe and Ojum (2025) on sustainable development in most regions of Nigeria, South – South inclusive remains undocumented.

According to Kenz and Blar (2024) sustainable development is the meeting of current needs without hunting the future generations' ability

to meet theirs. Ebekwu and Odione (2023) posited that sustainable development is all about building economic growth, social progress and protecting the environment. Sustainable development is like a balancing act that leads to economic growth, social inclusion and environmental protection. To achieve these goals there is need to equip individual with practical skills and knowledge that will enable them to function in the industries/establishments. In the same vein, Kalu and Sanusi (2023), in Nigeria much attention presently is been focused on renewable energy (solar, wind) together with sustainable agriculture and education to grow without harming the environment. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) is one of the educational training programmes that can equip individual with green skills for renewable energy (Ngwoke & Uwen, 2023).

Several studies such as (Amaechi & Uke, 2023; Mustapha, 2024; Natom & Tanbari, 2025) have revealed that regular policy reform programme is an effective strategy that must be adopted by government and stakeholders in education in order to reposition TVET programmes in Nigeria. According to Uzoego and Amakiri (2024), regular policy reform are crucial for Technical and Vocational and Training programmes in Nigeria to stay relevant and effective in line with global trends in education. Agwi and Eke (2024) posited that major reasons why regular policy reform of TVET programmes is necessary is that policy reforms can help TVET programmes adapt to changing industry requirement, ensuring graduates possess skill that match labour market demands, reform can also lead to better job prospects for graduates, addressing Nigeria's unemployment challenges, also policy reform in TVET can lead to increased funding, better infrastructure, and more resources for TVET Institutions. Despite these importance of regular policy reform in TVET programmes in Nigeria there are several

challenges facing TVET programmes in Nigeria (Ataliru & Mark, 2023).

Okonkwo and Ukwe (2025), posited that Nigeria's Technical and Vocational Education and Training sector faces several challenges, like inadequate funding, poor infrastructure and limited industry-academic collaboration. In South-South, Nigeria due to the rich oil and gas resources available in that region and growing services sector there is need for skilled workforce for sustainable development. Assessing Technical and Vocational Education and Training Policy reform impact can inform strategies to leverage TVET for regional growth in Nigeria. This study therefore, focuses on South-South, Nigeria examining how TVET policy reforms can contribute to sustainable development outcome like employment, entrepreneurship and environmental awareness.

Theoretical and Conceptual Clarifications Human Capital Theory by Gary Beker (1964)

Gary Beker is an American economist who developed the above theory. The theory states that investments in education, training, and skills development increase an individual productivity, earning, potential and economic growth. Beker said that investing in education, training, skills does the following to individual productivity, earning, potential and economic growth, it equips individuals with industry relevant skills, it boost productivity, it higher earning potential, it create job opportunity, human capital theory empowers people to start their own business, create job. Constant investment in education, training and skills development benefits individual with practical skills and knowledge that will help them to become productive that will eventually lead to economic growth. This is because Technical and Vocational Education and Training equips Nigerian's with practical skills for industries like construction and agriculture.

The relevance of this theory to this study stems from the fact that learners are expected to undergo effective practical training programmes in TVET programmes that will enable them to acquire practical digital skills that will help them to gainfully be employed or open up their own workshops upon graduation. The theory also help to explain how TVET programmes can help to boost skills (Human Capital) driven economic growth, and sustainability through investment in education. The theory made reasonable suggestions to TVET policy reform in Nigeria that training in TVET should focus on market-relevant skills, emphasize practical training and focus on sectors driving Nigeria's growth (e.g renewable energy, and digital skills).

Concept of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)

In their definition Mane and Sala (2024) sees Technical and Vocational Education and Training as a formal training in skills, knowledge, attributed technique or ability that an individual needs to have in order to do a particular job. Ibrahim and Olali (2024) sees Technical and Vocational Education and Training as the aspect of the general school curriculum concerned with the acquisition of knowledge, attitudes and skills necessary for securing and advancing in a given occupation. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) as defined by UNESCO (2012) adopted by Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) in her National Policy on Education is used as a comprehensive term referring to those aspect of educational process involving in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related science and the acquisition of practical skills, attitude, understanding and knowledge relating to occupation in various sectors of economic and social life.

Ezenekwe and Adegbero (2023) defined Technical and Vocational Education and

Training as a type of education that emphasizes preparation and participation in an occupation of social values. Technical and Vocational Education and Training is a field of study in the area of technology prepared to train and educate individual for skills and knowledge for entering into world of work. Technical and Vocational Education and Training is the aspect of education that leads to the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge. In the same vein Tanbowa and Taiwo (2022) echoed that Technical and Vocational Education and Training could be seen as an occupational education designed to develop a particular knowledge and skills associated with various technological patterns on individual that will enable them become self-reliant or gain employment in industries upon graduation. Similarly, Okereke and Uzodinma (2024) posited that TVET is a planned educational programmes of courses and learning experience that begins with exploration of career options, support basic academic and life skills, and enable achievement of high academic standards, leadership, preparation for industry-defined work an advance continuing education. The general goals of TVET according to Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) shall be to: provide the trained manpower in the applied sciences, technology and business particularly at craft, advance craft and technical level, provide the technical skills necessary for agricultural, commercial, and economic development, and to give training and impact the necessary skills to individual for self-reliance economically.

Concept of Policy Reform

Educational policy and reform are critical component of the education system that shape the way students are taught and the resources available to them. Educational policy according to Boaha (2025) refers to the rules, regulations, and guidelines that govern the education system. The author added that these

policies are put in place by government bodies, school boards and other organizations to ensure that students receive a quality education that prepares them for success in the workforce and in life. Educational reform on the other hand, involves making changes to existing policies and practices in order to improve the quality of education that will meet the needs of students. One of the key goals of educational policy and reform is to ensure that all students have access to a high-quality education, regardless of their background or socio-economic status. This includes providing resources such as technology, textbooks and other learning materials to help students succeed in their educational programme.

In Nigeria, TVET Policy refers to a written formal tool of thought through which formalized practices in TVET are made for decisions and actions towards strategic implementation in TVET by management and subordinates (Amakiri and Chinda, 2022). The Nigeria's TVET policy is enshrined in the document titled "National Policy on Education" which was first published in 1977 and revised in 1981, 1998, 2004, 2009 and 2013. Ojoba and Uza (2023) stated that the major educational reforms and policies in Africa and Nigeria in particular have been to restructure the inherited colonial education system with more emphasis on vocationalization. Over the years, Nigeria's TVET policy have evolved from one state to another. It was initially designed as "Technical Education" and later changed to "Technical and Vocational Education" in the year 2004 which later metamorphosed into Technical and Vocational Education and Training in the 2013 edition of National Policy on Education.

According to Echikwa and Nnaji (2025) the need for achieving the goal of policy reform in TVET cannot be overemphasized, therefore, it is important to create a better awareness and understanding on teachers who plays the role of implementing TVET policy reform.

Ozuruonye and Uke (2021) posited that when the teachers are fully aware or have better understanding of policy reform that the teachers will be able to effectively implement TVET policy reform that will positively lead to positive impact on sustainable development. According to Ijere and Eremie (2022) policy reform have significant impact on TVET in Nigeria. These impact according to the authors include; that policy reform will lead to a streamlined curriculum focusing on practical skills in sectors like construction, transportation, and oil and gas, policy reforms will increase access in the area like free tuition, accommodation and monthly stipends for students in TVET that will boost enrollment on TVET programmes, it will also lead to industry-linkage that will cause partnership with industries and international collaborations aim to align TVET with labour market needs.

Several studies such as (Agwi & Orji, 2021; Ugwuorah & Eke, 2024) reveals that several challenges are against effective implementation of educational policies including TVET policies in Nigeria. These challenges the authors added have adversely affected TVET contribution to sustainable development in Nigeria. In the same vein, Bamiyi and Abubarka (2024) identified faulty policy and institutional frameworks, political instability, lack of political will and corruption as major challenges or constraints against implementation of education policies generally. Nwankwo (2022) stated that inadequate funding; poor infrastructure, poor implementation, socio-economic factor, inadequate technology and lack of stakeholder engagement are major challenges that affect implementation of education policies in Nigeria.

Concept of Sustainable Development

The concept of sustainable development according to Brown (2025) can be interpreted in many different ways, but at its core is an approach to development that looks to balance

different, and often competing, needs against awareness or the environment, social and economic limitations we face as a society. According to Lukeman and Amankwa (2022) the concept of sustainable development remains one of the modern parameters of measuring development because it puts into consideration, the present conditions of people without compromising those that will come after. Sustainable development the authors added is the development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs. Sustainable development is manifested in improvement in the range of opportunities that would enable individuals and communities to achieve their aspiration and full potentials over a sustainable period of time while maintaining the resilience of economic, social and environmental system. In the same vein, Eluke (2020) posited that sustainable development in a community leads to national development which refers to the capacity of a country to raise the standard of living of its citizens by providing individuals with basic livelihood requirement and supplying them with employment. Akor and Onisoya (2024) maintained that the components of national development include development of rural areas, enlargement of economic knowledge, eradication of poverty, environmental security and self-reliance. A country is classified as developed when it is able to provide qualitative life to her citizens which can be accessed through increase in Gross Domestic Production (GDP), likely rates, availability of improved healthcare services, improvement in infrastructural facilities and considerable job opportunities among others (Howe, 2021). All these can be achieved through effective TVET programmes in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) policy reform in Nigeria is

aimed to drive economic growth and sustainable development. Unfortunately, some studies such as (Ojoba & Uza, 2023; Amakiri & Chinda, 2022) have shown that the impact of Technical and Vocational Education and Training policy reform on sustainable development in Nigeria, South-South inclusive remains unclear. According to Agwi and Orji (2021) in South-South region of Nigeria that despite the presence of numerous multinational oil companies that operates in South – South region, the region still struggles with the problem of youth unemployment, skill mismatch, an environmental degradation issues.

The lack of implementation of policy reform outcome in TVET has not only affected sustainable development goals in South – South region but has also affected the youths from acquiring useful practical skills and knowledge that can help them to be either gainfully employed in industries or open up their own private workshop upon their graduation. When these situations occur delay in the infrastructural and human development will begin to exist that may eventually lead to problems of youths restiveness, cyber crime, kidnapping, armed robbery among other social vices as witnessed in the country at present. Therefore, there is a compelling need to explore how the impact of TVET policy reform can help to achieve sustainable development in South – South region of Nigeria. This study seeks to address this gap by assessing the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to assess the impact of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) policy reform on sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Assess the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria.
2. Examine the impacts of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria.
3. Identify challenges for enhancing Technical and Vocational Education and training (TVET) contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria?
2. What are the impacts of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria?
3. What are the challenges for enhancing Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on the impacts of TVET policy reforms on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on challenges for

enhancing Technical and Vocational Education and Training contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. According to Nworgu cited in Agwi and Orji (2021) descriptive survey design is aimed at collecting data on and describing in systematic manner the characteristic feature or facts about a given population or representative or existing phenomena. The population of the study was 217 (comprising 172 male TVET educators and 45 female TVET educators) in the 12 universities in South-South, Nigeria that offer programmes in Technology Education as at 2025/2026 academic session. These universities include; Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolemini, Port Harcourt, Niger Delta University, Amasoma, Bayelsa State, University of Uyo, Akwa-Ibom State, University of Benin, Ambrose Ali University, Ekpoma, Delta State University, Abraka, Cross Rivers State, University of Technology.

A self-structured 27-item questionnaire designed by the researchers title “Impact of TVET Policy Reform on Sustainable Development Questionnaire” (ITPRSD) was the instrument used for the data collection from the respondents. The instrument was constructed on a a-4 point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was face and content validated by three experts in Technology Education Department from Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State. The instrument reliability was ascertained with the use of Cronbach’s alpha correlation method in which a reliability of 0.80 was obtained. A total of 145 copies of the research instrument was administered to the

respondents directly by the researchers with the help of five (5) research assistants. The total number of copies of the completed instrument retrieved after two weeks was 135 (95 male TVET educators and 40 female TVET educators) representing 98 percent return. The completed instrument was considered adequate and were used for the analysis of the study.

Mean and Standard deviation were the statistical tools used to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested with t-test statistical technique at the 0.05 level of significance. To arrive at a decision on the research questions, real limit of numbers were used. Any item statement that had mean value of 2.50 and above was regarded as “Agree” while item statement that

falls below 2.50 was regarded as “Disagree”. The standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the respondents mean rating. In testing the hypotheses, the null hypotheses were not rejected if the calculated t-value is less and equal to the critical t-value on the other hand were the calculated t-value is greater than the critical t-value the null hypotheses were rejected.

Results

The results of the study are presented in Tables 1-6 in line with the research questions and hypotheses.

Research Question 1: What are the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Impact of TVET Policy Reform on Sustainable Development among Educators in TVET

S/N	Awareness and Understanding	Male TVET Educators N = 95			Female TVET Educators N = 40		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	TVET educators have good understanding of TVET policy reform in Nigeria.	2.53	0.71	Agree	2.50	0.69	Agree
2.	TVET educators are aware of the current TVET policy reform in Nigeria.	2.64	0.75	Agree	2.51	0.70	Agree
3.	TVET educators are familiar with computer based Test reform policy.	2.73	0.79	Agree	2.55	0.72	Agree
4.	TVET educators are aware of the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development.	2.69	0.72	Agree	2.59	0.73	Agree
5.	TVET policy reform are effectively implemented in your institution.	2.31	0.68	Disagree	2.21	0.61	Disagree
6.	There are benefits of TVET policy reform to sustainable development.	2.19	0.63	Disagree	2.15	0.60	Disagree
7.	There challenges that hinder effective implementation of TVET policy reform.	2.72	0.77	Agree	2.68	0.72	Agree
8.	There are adequate support/training on TVET policy reform in your institution.	2.18	0.62	Disagree	2.10	0.60	Disagree
Average Mean/SD		2.55	0.71		2.51	0.67	

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Result in Table 1 on awareness and understanding of impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria shows that both male TVET educators and female TVET educators agreed that most of the variables highlighted are the impact TVET educators on the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria. This is evident in the Grand Mean Scores of 2.55 for

male TVET educators and 2.51 for female TVET educators which are both greater than the acceptable mean score of 2.50 earlier stated. Also, the closeness of the Standard Deviation for the both groups which is 0.71 and 0.67 shows homogeneity in the responses of both groups.

Research Question 2: What are the impacts of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on Impacts of TVET Policy Reform on Sustainable Development Outcomes in South – South, Nigeria

S/N	Impacts	Male TVET Educators N = 95			Female TVET Educators N = 40		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
	ITEMS						
9.	TVET reforms have improved skills alignment with industry needs.	2.81	0.78	Agree	2.63	0.72	Agree
10.	TVET policy reforms have influenced job creation.	2.89	0.79	Agree	2.68	0.75	Agree
11.	TVET have impacted entrepreneurship among graduates	2.88	0.78	Agree	2.65	0.74	Agree
12.	TVET have impacted on the effectiveness in promoting environmental sustainability.	2.67	0.75	Agree	2.55	0.70	Agree
13.	TVET policy reforms have improved access to TVET programmes.	2.89	0.78	Agree	2.72	0.77	Agree
14.	TVET policy reforms have helped to reduce unemployment rate.	2.81	0.79	Agree	2.58	0.71	Agree
15.	TVET policy have influenced infrastructure development post reform.	2.83	0.80	Agree	2.61	0.72	Agree
16.	TVET policy reforms have influenced industry partnership and collaboration.	2.79	0.76	Agree	2.63	0.73	Agree
17.	TVET policy reform have helped to promote innovation and technical adoption.	2.76	0.69	Agree	2.59	0.70	Agree
	Average Mean/SD	2.53	0.69		2.51	0.62	

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Result in Table 2 on the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria shows that both male TVET educators and female TVET educators agreed that all the variables highlighted are impacts of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria. This is evident in the

Grand Mean Scores of 2.53 for male TVET educators and 2.51 for female TVET educators, which are both greater than the acceptable mean score of 2.50 earlier stated. Also, the closeness of the Standard Deviation for the both groups which is 0.69 and 0.62 shows homogeneity in the responses of both groups.

Research Question 3: What are the challenges for enhancing technical and vocational education and training (TVET) contributions

to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Respondents on Challenges for Enhancing TVET Contribution to Sustainable Development in South – South, Nigeria.

S/N	Challenges	Male TVET Educators N = 95			Female TVET Educators N = 40		
		\bar{X}	SD	Remark	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
	ITEMES						
18.	Funding constraints hinder TVET programmes.	2.95	0.88	Agree	2.85	0.78	Agree
19.	Industry partnership are insufficient.	2.87	0.85	Agree	3.00	0.82	Agree
20.	Infrastructure and equipment are inadequate.	2.91	0.87	Agree	2.68	0.75	Agree
21.	TVET educators lack regular training.	3.00	0.89	Agree	2.75	0.70	Agree
22.	Limited access to tech and digital tools.	3.10	0.91	Agree	2.81	0.72	Agree
23.	Poor public perception of TVET.	2.98	0.88	Agree	2.85	0.78	Agree
24.	Policy implementation of TVET is weak.	3.04	0.90	Agree	2.67	0.74	Agree
25.	Monitoring and evaluation are inadequate.	3.15	0.93	Agree	2.85	0.78	Agree
26.	Limited Research and Development in TVET.	3.18	0.94	Agree	2.76	0.71	Agree
27.	Inadequate industry – relevant curriculum updates.	2.85	0.84	Agree	2.55	0.69	Agree
	Average Mean/SD	3.00	0.89		2.78	0.84	

Source: Field Survey, 2026

Result in Table 3 on the challenges for enhancing technical and vocational education and training (TVET) contribution to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria, shows that both male TVET educators and female TVET educators agreed that all the variables highlighted are challenges for enhancing TVET contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria. This is evident in the Grand Mean Scores of 3.00 for male TVET educators and 2.78 for female TVET educators, which are both greater than the acceptable mean score of 2.50 earlier

stated. Also, the closeness of the Standard Deviation for the both groups which is 0.89 and 0.84 shows homogeneity in the responses of both groups.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria.

Table 4: t-test for Responses on Impact of TVET Policy Reform on Sustainable Development in South – South

Groups	N	M	SD	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male TVET Educators	95	2.55	0.71	0.17	1.96	Accepted
Female TVET Educators	40	2.51	0.51			

Result in Table 4 shows that t cal. was 0.17 while t-crit. was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that t-cal was less than t-crit, hence, the null hypothesis was accepted which means that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on the impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development

among educators in TVET Programmes in South – South, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on the impacts of TVET policy reforms on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria.

Table 5: t-test for Responses on Impact of TVET Policy Reform on Sustainable Development Outcomes in South – South, Nigeria

Groups	N	M	SD	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male TVET Educators	95	2.76	0.69	0.19	1.96	Accepted
Female TVET Educators	40	2.53	0.62			

Result in Table 5 shows that t cal. was 0.19 while t-crit. was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that t-cal was less than t-crit, hence, the null hypothesis was accepted which means that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on the impact of TVET policy reform on

sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on challenges for enhancing TVET contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria.

Table 6: t-test for Responses on Challenges for Enhancing TVET contributions to Sustainable Development in South – South, Nigeria

Groups	N	M	SD	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
Male TVET Educators	95	3.00	0.89	0.21	1.96	Accepted
Female TVET Educators	40	2.78	0.84			

Result in Table 6 shows that t cal. was 0.21 while t-crit. was 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This implies that t-cal was less than t-crit, hence, the null hypothesis was accepted which means that there was no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female TVET educators on challenges for enhancing TVET contributions to sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria.

educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria shows that both male and female TVET educators agreed that most of the variables highlighted are the awareness and understanding of impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among educators in TVET programmes in South – South, Nigeria. This is evident in the Grand Mean Scores of 2.55 for male TVET educators and 2.51 for female TVET educators which are both greater than the acceptable mean score of 2.50 earlier stated. Also, the closeness of the Standard Deviation for the both groups which is 0.69 and 0.62 shows homogeneity in the responses of both groups. This is in conformity

Discussion

Result in Table 1 above on awareness and understanding of impact of TVET policy reform on sustainable development among

with the findings of Ozuruonye and Uke (2021) who stated that when teachers are fully aware or have better understanding of policy reform that the teachers will be able to effectively implement TVET policy reform that will lead to positive impact on sustainable development programmes.

Result in Table 2 above on the impacts of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria shows that both male and female TVET educators agreed that all the variables highlighted are the impacts of TVET policy reform on sustainable development outcomes in South – South, Nigeria. This is evident in the Grand Mean Scores of 2.53 for male TVET educators and 2.51 for female TVET educators which are both greater than the acceptable mean score of 2.50 earlier stated. Also, the closeness of the Standard Deviation for the both groups which is 0.69 and 0.62 shows homogeneity in the responses of both groups. This is in line with Ijere and Eremie (2022) who stated that policy reform programme in TVET have significant impact on sustainable development goals, these impacts according to the authors include; that policy reform will lead to a streamlined curriculum focusing on practical skills in sector like construction and transportation, policy reform will help to increase access in the area like free tuition, accommodation and monthly stipends for students in TVET.

Result in Table 3 above on challenges for enhancing TVET contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria show that both male and female TVET educators agreed that all the variables highlighted are challenges for enhancing TVET contributions to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria. This is evident in the Grand Mean Scores of 3.00 for male TVET educators and 2.78 for female TVET educators which are both greater than the acceptable mean score of

2.50 earlier stated. Also, the closeness of the Standard Deviation for the both groups which is 0.89 and 0.84 shows homogeneity in the responses of both groups. This is in consonance with previous studies by Bamiyi and Abubaka (2024) who found that faulty policy and institutional frameworks, political instability, lack of political will and corruption are major challenges or constraints against implementation of education policies in Nigeria.

Conclusion

From the findings of this study, it was deduced that regular, policy reform in technical and vocational education and training programme that prepare learners for the world of work and sustainable development is an effective programme that can help to improve the quality of TVET programme in Nigeria. However, despite the relevant of Policy reform in TVET, it was deduced that several challenges constrain the implementation of policy reform in TVET programme that can enhance sustainable development, such as poor funding, lack of political will and corruption, faulty policy and institutional framework. Also, poor infrastructure, limited access to tech and digital tools, lack of regular training TVET educators are challenges for enhancing TVET contribution to sustainable development in South – South, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are suggested:

1. Government should ensure that regular training of TVET educators are always organize as to help TVET educators to update their knowledge on how to implement policy reform on TVET programme.

2. More technical and vocational training institutions should be established by government in all the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria in order to train more learners that will function in the industries/establishment in Nigeria.
3. Adequate fund should be released by the government annually through budget as to effectively manage TVET programmes in Nigeria.

References

- Agwi, V.I & Eke, N. E (2024). Teachers' perception on policy change implementation, strategies adoption in technical colleges in Rivers State. *Journal of Educational Research*. 6(1), 30-45.
- Agwi, V. I & Orji, V. N. (2021). Implementation of policy reform in technical and vocational education and training in the 21st century: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*. 8(1), 50 – 65.
- Akpan, E. M. (2024). The impact of technical education in national development in the 21st century educational landscape.
- Akor, E.S & Onisoaya, L.C (2024). Effective technical and vocational education and training programmes for sustainable national development: Issues and way forward. *Journal of Academic Excellence*. 6(1), 100-115.
- Amakiri, O.T. & Chinda, N.K. (2023). TVET policies in Nigeria: Why the gap. *Journal of Education and Development*. 10(1), 20-35
- Amaechi, S.G & Uke, T.N. (2023). The need for regular policy reform in TVET for sustainable nation development.
- Atahitu, M. & Mark, F. E (2022). Challenges of effective technical and vocational education and training policy reform in Nigeria: The way forward.
- Boaha, F.K. (2025). Policy innovation in the VTE sector: The role of teachers in competency – based training in Australia TVET Institutions. *European Journal in Training and Development Studies*. 12(1), 90 – 105.
- Brown, L.T.(2025). Educational policy in Nigeria: Challenges of implementation and ways forward. *European Journal of Educational Studies*. 8(1) 40 – 55.
- Ebekwu, G. I & Odione, M. A. (2023), Achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria through effect TVET programmes: Issues, challenges and ways forward. *Journal Vocational and Technology Education*. 6(1), 80 – 95.
- Echikwa, B. N. & Nnaji, C. C (2023). Lessons for the Nigerian government towards sustainable industrial growth. *Technical and vocational Education Journal*. 7(1), 60 – 75.
- Ejimaiji, E. A & Nwankwo, S. E (2023). Educational policies and problems of implementing in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Research*. 14(1), 120 – 135.
- Eluke, F. N. (2020). The role of TVET in achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria in the 21st century.
- Ezenekwe, B. O & Adegbero, N. E. (2023). Critical appraisal of TVET policies in Nigeria and their implementation challenges.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013). National Policy on Education (Revised 6th Edition): Lagos NERDC Press.
- Howe, C.T (2021). Effective strategies required for achieving sustainable development goals in Ghana: Implementation challenges and way forward.
- Ibekwe, W. E. & Ojum, A. N. (2025). Impact of TVET policy reform in national productivity n Nigeria: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Academic Excellence*. 8(1), 50 – 65
- Ibrahim, A. & Olali, U. G. (2024). TVET policy reform in Nigeria 2010 – 2023, between human capital and the right to education. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*. 9(1&2), 60 – 75.
- Ijleri, B. N & Eremie, N. K. (2022). TVET models, structure and policy reform evidence from Nigeria and Ghana.
- Ikwazu, U. I & Ugwu, F. O. (2025), *TVET policy reform in Nigeria: An effective strategy for achieving sustainable development goals in Nigeria*.
- Kalu, M.E & Sanusi, A. M. (2022). Challenges in implementation of TVET policy reform agenda in Nigeria. Issues , challenges and way forward. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas*. 6(1), 90 – 105
- Kenz, F.G & Blar, A. O (2024). Evaluation of sustainable development programmes in Ghana for human and capital development goals.
- Lukeman, E. S. & Amarukwa, O. (2022). Security education: An imperative for Ghana's

- development. *Journal of Education*. 12(1), 60 – 75.
- Mane, E. L. & Sala, M. K (2024). Technical and Vocational Education and Training: A useful means of producing highly technical trained personnel for sustainable national development.
- Mustapha, B. A. (2024). The need for effective policy reform in Nigeria education system. *Journal of Educational Research*. 5(1), 30 – 45.
- Naton, U. & Tambari, O. A. (2025). Principles and application of educational policies: Nsukka: University Trust Publishers.
- Ngwoke, E. N. & Umaru, A. M. (2023). Technology educators perception of their challenges in implementing TVET policy reform in Enugu State. *Journal of vocational and Technology Education*. 11(1), 10 – 15.
- Nwankwo, W. E. (2022). Challenges of implementing TVET policy reform in South – East, Nigeria.
- Ojoba, E. O & Uza, T. F (2023). Issues and challenges in TVET policy reform in the 21st century Education Landscape. *International Journal of Education*. 13(1), 40 – 55.
- Okereke, E. G. & Uzodima, F. O. (2024). Vocational and technical education as a catalyst for achieving the aims of job creation in Imo State, *Nigerian vocational Association Journal*. 8(1), 50 – 65.
- Okonkwo, L. I. & Ukwe, B. O. (2025). Strategies for tackling TVET programmes in Abia State for sustainable development. *Journal of Academic Excellence*. 12 (1), 10 – 15.
- Ozurumba, B. E & Uke, W. O (2021). Technology educators understanding of the impact of TVET policy reform in Rivers State. *International Journal of Humanities*. 8(1&2), 30 – 45.
- Tambari, S. B. & Taiwo, C. T. (2022). TVET as mechanism for sustainable development in Nigeria (SD): Potential challenges and policy prescription.
- Ugwurah, C. M & Eke, N. U. (2024). Challenges against effective implementation of TVET policy reform in Nigeria.
- Uzoego, N. & Amakiri, F. K. (2024). Strategies for regular policy reform in Nigerian Educational System in the 21st century: Issue and challenges. *Journal of Vocational Education*. 10(1), 60 – 75.